

Planet RDC Focus Area 2: Integrated FAIR Datasets and Services

Program 2.1: National-scale Integrated Datasets and Services (NIDAS)

Program Guidelines

The purpose of these guidelines is to provide potential project partners with the program strategy and intended outcomes, and clear guidance around expectations for projects.

Program Overview	1
Program Outcomes	2
Project Requirements	3
In Scope Activities	4
Out of Scope Activities	4
Process and Timeline	5
Investment and Duration	5
ARDC expectations for the conduct of co-investment projects	6

Revision History

Version	Date	Editor	Summary of changes
0.1	14 Feb 2024	Julia Martin	Draft
0.9	26 Feb 2024	Hamish Holewa	DRAFT Feedback and revision
1.0	1 Jul 2024	Julia Martin	Incorporating all feedback. Version for publication.
2.0	18 Feb 2025	Julia Martin	Updated to reflect new dates and budget.
2.1	06 Mar 2025	Julia Martin	Incorporating all feedback. Version for publication.

Program Overview

Researchers need to be able to understand, predict and report changes to the environment at a faster pace than ever before. To do so requires national scale FAIR data plus robust services that are integrated and interoperable. The earth and environmental sciences (EES) address complex challenges that require multidisciplinary research, however, finding, accessing and standardising data for cross-domain analysis is still resource intensive. Data is often too disparate and heterogeneous to be easily interoperable. The National-scale Integrated Datasets and Services (NIDAS) program will target specific data mobilisation and integration activities and next generation national data services to enable researchers, government and industry to easily access and analyse FAIR earth and environmental sciences data. This program is part of the [Planet Research Data Commons](#).

Research institutions and government agencies produce high-impact but long-tail data across many EES disciplines. Accessing and managing the large number of heterogeneous datasets is challenging for researchers. When data is generated, the outputs rarely conform to agreed standards, inhibiting integration and compatibility with national services. The NIDAS program will support the development of national data assets that are FAIR, high quality and machine actionable, enabling integration with existing national services. The focus will be on equipping data managers with the tools and capability to deliver standardised datasets for new research, industry innovation and government decision making.

Through its corporate knowledge and data publishing products, ARDC is uniquely placed to lead the delivery of these cross-discipline FAIR data assets, tools and services. The national data assets will facilitate the accessibility and usability of valuable data that are crucial for climate change research, evidence based policy for environmental management plus government initiatives that help shape strategy, policy and action, such as the State of the Environment report, nature positive outcomes and reporting processes.

The ARDC will work with key research, government and industry stakeholders including DCCEEW, NCRIS, state agencies, industry partners and universities, with a focus on establishing cross-sector partnerships to enable research translation.

The NIDAS program will enable:

- Mobilisation of specific national data assets across government and research including integration with national services;
- Development of cross domain capability and capacity in implementation of data standards for multi-domain data integration;
- Development and provision of reusable data tools and services that enable FAIR data provision (with an emphasis on machine readability and accessibility);
- Building of consensus on standards and adoption capability amongst the research sector and our NCRIS partners;

- Enduring retention of data assets.

Each project will establish appropriate business models and data governance. Practices to make data FAIR, stakeholder consensus on agreed standards & best practices for data, metadata, vocabularies, data exchange, quality, provenance, and trusted repositories for data retention.

The projects within the program will utilise ARDC expertise and publishing services, including Research Data Australia, Research Vocabularies Australia, as well as Persistent Identifiers. Underlying storage and compute infrastructure will be available where appropriate.

The Planet RDC is an integrated set of Focus Areas and Activities. Outputs and outcomes will be utilised and receive guidance by other Planet RDC Focus Areas. Data, and data services will be made available to researchers via Planet RDC infrastructure as appropriate.

Program Outcomes

Key results areas where Planet RDC Activity 2.1 will deliver value to research, government and industry through the NIDAS program include:

- Enduring and trusted integrated data, information products and national infrastructure and services that form the building blocks for the assessment of cumulative impact, State of the Environment reporting, environmental economic accounting, the nature repair market, and accurate environmental prediction and trend reporting.
- A partnership model for government, industry, research and NRI to optimise earth and environmental data and information, resulting in better, more integrated research
- Strengthening the availability of data for research and reporting
- Research translation to government and industry to support evidence-based decision making

Project Requirements

- Projects will create and retain national scale, integrated and standardised datasets or services that meet specific research needs or research translation use cases.
- Data Integration efforts must be documented for the purpose of future integration projects, even when the dataset is not publicly available.
- Research needs or research translation use cases will be clearly defined.
- The datasets are made interoperable and accessible through the adoption of community agreed standards and services, specifically:
 - Persistent identifiers that align with the National PID Strategy
 - Community agreed vocabularies, published in Research Vocabularies Australia
 - Rich metadata for each project output, harvested into Research Data Australia
- Projects will be identified through the Planet RDC national consultation and co-design process.
- There are clear documented links to National Research Infrastructure, including platforms and/or services.
- There is linkage to government and industry, including translation opportunities where possible.
- Projects should cover multiple disciplines in the earth and environmental sciences
- Projects will develop enduring partnerships needed to support the national data asset.
- Infrastructure developed or enhanced during the project is documented, enduring and sustainable after the end of the project
- Existing standards, infrastructure and other resources are expected to be documented and adopted where possible or adapted where necessary
- Infrastructure should be available and useful nationally, and where this is not possible (for business model or security reasons) the system must be documented so it can be easily replicated by another ARDC partnership
- Project teams will actively share and collaborate with other ARDC projects including sharing of outputs, knowledge, communications and infrastructure when relevant

In Scope Activities

A project to deliver national scale datasets and services could include the following activities:

- Establishing partnerships with cross-jurisdictional or cross-sector stakeholders, through workshops and meetings leading to formal data sharing agreements
- Defining a sustainability plan for the outputs from the NIDAS project, with early agreement from stakeholders, including the target data stewards/curators.
- Mapping the capabilities required to deliver the identified products to the [SAFE](#) framework, and identifying maturity and gaps in those capabilities
- Implementing FAIR data through community agreed data and metadata standards, vocabularies, identifiers.
- Producing data assets or information products to meet the researcher use cases
- Building (or enhancing existing) and operating digital infrastructure(s) to enable the NIDAS, for example, Data Spaces based on international standards
- Defining and implementing standards across environmental indicator data
- Other activities as co-designed by ARDC and project stakeholders

Out of Scope Activities

ARDC cannot invest directly in the following (although other partners may provide these outputs as part of the project):

- Sampling or surveying to fill data gaps
- Research.

Process and Timeline

The Planet RDC is following a community co-design process to deliver its programs.

- 2022
 - National consultation and policy analysis identified major national stakeholders and national priorities.
- 2023
 - Identification of priorities and strategy release.
- 2024
 - Q1 - Project shaping phase - we will hold meetings with potential delivery partners and stakeholders to identify and select potential solution(s) and finalise the project team(s).
 - Q2 - Project planning phase, where we will work with identified project partners to develop an investable project plan.
 - Q3 onwards - Project delivery for the first tranche of NIDAS projects.
- 2025
 - Q1 - Project shaping phase for remaining NIDAS projects.
 - Q2 - Project planning phase for remaining NIDAS projects.
 - Q3 onwards - Project delivery for remaining NIDAS projects.

Investment and Duration

The total ARDC budget for the NIDAS program is \$1.273 million over 4 years (2024-2027).

The project duration is up to two years, with an expectation that the new data assets and services and related infrastructure will be enduring and maintained on an ongoing basis following the formal project phase.

ARDC policy requires a minimum of 1:1 co-investment ratio between ARDC's investment and that of all the other project participants combined. See the [ARDC's Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details.

ARDC expectations for the conduct of co-investment projects

- Project partners will match ARDC co-investment at a minimum 1:1 ratio. Both cash and in-kind co-investment are acceptable. All co-investments must be made in an auditable form (see the [ARDC's Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details).
- Projects must be aligned with the [NCRIS 2023 Guidelines](#) and the Principles set out in the [NRI Roadmap](#) (pg 14 pdf, pg 21 doc).
- Projects must have a dedicated project manager with appropriate experience and capacity. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the naming of a specific Technical Lead and Research.
- Projects must have an ARDC-agreed governance structure to ensure desired outcomes are met. This may require a program-wide steering committee (including members not directly involved in the delivery of the projects) with defined Terms of Reference that meets at least quarterly. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the formation of a user reference group.
- Projects are required to commit to monthly traffic light reporting and other reporting requirements specified at contracting.
- Project plans must include the tracking of desired outcomes, including measuring the uptake of infrastructure by the research community, industry and government with clear KPIs that evidence the value to research, government and industry.
- Project plans should include user testing of ideas and prototype outputs early and often throughout project delivery.
- Most outputs will require ongoing operation beyond the life of the project in order to realise the intended benefits. Project plans must include a statement of the minimum ongoing maintenance likely to be required (both duration and resources) and a plan for that maintenance (to be agreed between ARDC and the project partners).
- Project outputs (including software) should be made as FAIR as possible, and the infrastructure developed should make research outputs FAIR for reuse and reproducibility. See the [ARDC guideline for FAIR data](#), [FAIR for Research Software](#), and [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments](#).
- Project teams are expected to collaborate across the Planet RDC and other ARDC-supported projects, as relevant and directed by the ARDC, to meet program objectives.
- Project teams are expected to attend and contribute to relevant ARDC workshops and events.
- Project teams are expected to engage in communication activities to raise awareness of their project and attract a growing user base within the earth and environmental sciences community. When doing so, projects need to acknowledge ARDC and NCRIS using the wording [provided by ARDC](#).